

Traditional Agricultural Practices of Bodo community

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Bodo community, an indigenous group primarily residing in the northeastern part of India, has a rich history of traditional agricultural practices. These practices are deeply rooted in their culture, providing sustenance, livelihood and a sense of identity. The traditional agricultural practices of this community demonstrate a deep understanding of local ecosystems and sustainable resource management. The present research paper aims to explore the traditional agricultural practices of the Bodo tribe. The study investigates the historical, cultural and ecological aspects of Bodo agriculture, highlighting its sustainable and community-centered nature. By examining the traditional knowledge and techniques employed by the Bodo tribe, this paper seeks to provide insights into their unique agricultural practices and their relevance in the face of modern challenges. The findings of this research paper contribute to the preservation of indigenous knowledge systems and offer potential pathways for the sustainable development of rural communities.